

A Comprehensive Survey on Cyber Security Threats in IoT-Enabled Banking Sector

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Abstract - The rise of the Internet of things (IOT) in the banking industry sector has change the way financial organizations operate, making services easier and more convenient for customers. However, with these benefits there are some cybersecurity risks including phishing, DDoS attacks, unauthorized access, malware attacks, fraud, Ransomware and many more. This study analyzes the cybersecurity threats by collecting information from customers through a survey, cybersecurity experts and also banking professionals. The survey explores the effectiveness of security measures and awareness among stakeholders, the goal is to comprehend the most pressing security concerns, to evaluate how the current protections are working and identify lacks or problems that needs be solved. the findings concentrate on emerging security challenges and offer solutions for strengthening security in IOT-enabled banking industry, to be prepare ahead for these threats with advanced security protocols to help the financial organizations and customers from cyber threats.

Keyword – *Banking Security, IoT Devices, Cyber Security vulnerability, threats, malware*

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in banking is transforming financial services by streamlining processes, enhancing customer convenience, and improving operational efficiency. Banks are increasingly leveraging smart technologies such as connected ATMs, wearable payment devices, biometric authentication systems, and NFC-enabled POS terminals to offer faster and more personalized services. These IoT systems communicate across networks, continuously collecting and transmitting data to improve financial decision-making, track assets, and provide real-time insights.

For example, IoT sensors installed in ATMs can alert banks about hardware malfunctions, enabling swift maintenance to minimize downtime [1]. Similarly, IoT-connected payment terminals in retail environments allow secure contactless transactions, improving customer convenience. These developments are crucial in modern banking as financial institutions strive to meet growing customer demands for speed, security, and digital transformation.

Despite these benefits, IoT systems in banking also introduce new cybersecurity concerns. IoT devices [2] often have modest processing power and memory, hindering their ability to aid advance security features that is used by these systems. Furthermore, many IoT endpoints are designed with minimal security protocols [3], making them attractive targets for cyber attackers. As banks connect thousands of IoT devices to their networks, the risk of attacks such as data breaches, malware infiltration, and DDoS campaigns increases dramatically [4].

Table 1 A Summary on Cyber Threats, Their Threat Actors and Their Objectives

Threat	Level	Threat actors	Objectives
Cyber Vandalism	1	Hackers, vandalist, angered employees, activist	Data stealing, destroying, or public posting for media coverage
Cyber Theft	2	Individual, small groups (political, ideology), spammers	Information disruption of destruction of business operations, profit or ideological gains
Cyber Incursion	3	Structured enterprise, government institution, and terrorist bands	Information weakness, backdoor planting, access, alter or destroy information.

Cyber Sabotage	4	Structured professional entities, military top-secret operators	High-level information regarding secret R&D critical for organization/government, cracking security procedures, infiltration
Cyber Conflict	5	Government workers, skilled terrorist teams, Advance hacker teams	Infrastructure destruction, high importance mission critical information
Cyber Internal	6	Employees, workers, third party service providers	Non-international mistakes, carelessness, lack of skill to open opportunities for 1 to 5 discussed threats

The consequences of cybersecurity threats in IoT-driven banking systems [5] are far-reaching. Successful attacks may result in financial losses, data exposure, reputational damage, and legal penalties. Attackers exploiting IoT vulnerabilities can intercept financial transactions, compromise customer accounts, or disrupt banking operations. As IoT adoption continues to expand, financial institutions must understand these threats and adopt proactive measures to safeguard their infrastructure and customer data [6].

This research makes several meaningful contributions to the field of Internet of Things System security in the banking industry:

- It outlines various types of cybersecurity threats targeting IoT-enabled banking services, including data theft, DDoS attacks, and identity spoofing.
- The study identifies vulnerable points within IoT ecosystems that pose the highest security risks for financial institutions.
- Practical mitigation strategies such as secure encryption, device security standards, and blockchain solutions are explored to provide actionable insights for banks to enhance their security framework.
- The research incorporates real-world case studies to illustrate the potential risks faced by banks and demonstrate the effectiveness of proposed security measures.
- Lastly, this study bridges the gap between academic research and industry application, providing financial institutions with effective solutions to address emerging IoT security challenges.

By combining technical analysis with practical security strategies, this research aims to support banks in building resilient IoT ecosystems that promote secure financial services while reducing exposure to cyber threats.

II. BACKGROUND ON CYBER SECURITY THREATS

As banks continue to rapidly embrace digital transformation, the Internet of Things (IoT) is emerging as a key enabler by enhancing customer services by providing real-time transaction processing, improving fraud detection, and automating financial services. IOT-enabled banking Industries utilizes interconnected devices such as banking Applications, Smart ATMs, Wearable payment devices, Wearable payment devices to enhance customer experience efficiently.

However, the IoT are lack standardized protocols, resource-constrained, and operate over public networkers which lead them to cyber threats such as [7]:

- unauthorized access to banking Industry networks,
- malware attacks compromising IoT systems,
- data breaches and financial frauds due to the weak encryption
- Man –in-the-Middle (MITM) attacks can intercept the sensitive transactions

Fig. 1. Benefits of IoT in banking

1. IoT in Banking Industry and security Implications

With the IoT, Banking Industries have been transformed by allowing the interconnectivity between financial services and digital devices:

A). Banking Devices and ATMs:

The Smart ATMs are connected to Banking networks, they allow real-time cash monitoring and predictive maintenance by using IoT sensors and cloud connectivity.

Hackers exploit ATMs through unauthorized network access, malware injection and also by skimming devices.

B). Biometric authentication systems

Those are fingerprint scanner, facial recognition used to secure account access.

These are strong encryption to identify theft and unauthorized access

C). IoT driven fraud Detection

They are AI-powered security systems used to prevent frauds and analyze real time transactions.

The cybercriminals exploit these systems by manipulating Models by introducing adversarial inputs to trick the system.

D). Connected (POS) systems

They are retail payment terminal systems integrated in Banking Networks for seamless Transactions.

Weak encryption and unsecured networks lead to cybercriminals to intercept transactions and conduct to fraud

2. Benefits of IoT in Banking Industry

In Banking Industry, IoT offers various benefits such as:

A). Improve customer experience

By using Smart ATMs, IoT-powered ATMs can detect issues, monitor cash level, and request maintenance automatically [8].

Customer withdraw their money using Biometrics cards or mobile authentication instead of traditional cards

B). Intelligent Automation

IoT help banks to automate processes and this reduce errors and increase productivity.

C). Enhance fraud detection and security

IoT (Biometric authentication, IoT-based fraud detection, Block chain for fraud detection) has a strength security in Banking and this help to prevent significantly frauds and unauthorized transactions [9].

D). Data Analytics

Banks utilize IoT-generated data to obtain insights into their customer’s behavior and then improve financial services

3. Types of IoT security attacks

A). Communication attacks

These are attacks occur when data is being transmitted between IoT devices and servers. IoT Devices often rely on wireless network, then hackers can manipulate the communication. For example, in Man-In –The –Middle attack, the hackers intercept data which are being transmitted between IoT devices and servers and modify it without user’s knowledge. To prevent this, Banking industry are recommended to encrypt data transmission, implementing authentication mechanism and use secure communication protocol.

B). Attacks on the device software

These are attacks happening through the vulnerabilities of software or firmware of IoT devices. For example, hackers can modify IoT firmware and insert malicious code. In order to prevent this, Banking has regularly to update their IoT firmware and software.

C). Life cycle attacks

Life cycle attacks happen when IoT device transitions between multiples stages of use such as from manufacturing to end-users. To prevent this, Banks have to use secure firmware update mechanism and encrypt stored data to prevent unauthorized access.

Fig. 2 Types of IoT security attacks

Physical attacks happen when hackers directly tamper with IoT device’s hardware to extract sensitive information or to manipulate its behavior. For example, a hacker can extract the encryption key from a stolen IoT security camera

and then physically open the device to extract sensitive data from memory chips. To prevent this tamper-resistant hardware has to be used and apply physical security measure.

4. Need for a cybersecurity survey on IoT-enabled Banking Industry

IoT-based financial systems remain highly vulnerable to cyberattacks despite advancement in banking cybersecurity frameworks. Cyber threats are increasing sophisticatedly and necessitates a comprehensive survey to:

Evaluate regularly the effectiveness of the current security framework

Propose strategic recommendations to enhance cybersecurity resilience in IoT banking Environments to identify most common and emerging cyber threats in IoT-enabled Banking industry [10].

III. ANALYZING CYBER SECURITY THREATS THAT RELATES TO THE BANKING INDUSTRY

The banking industry is the literally the backbone of our modern economies, providing financial services that range from saving accounts and loans to complex investment mechanisms. With rapid digital changes, banks have embraced technology to enhance customer experience, streamline operations, and increase efficiency. However, delving into this technologies advancement has also made banks' prime targets for cybercriminals. Cyber threats to banking institutions have grown exponentially, hunting not just financial assets but also customer trust and economic stability.

Basic components of banking systems with the various cybersecurity threats they face, and the sophisticated attacks methods employed by cybercriminals are reasons why banking sectors and modern banks consists of numerous technological and operational components, each susceptible to different cyber threats.

The components are: Core Banking System (CBS) which is the heart of banking operations that deals with managing transactions, customer data, and account details in real time. Digital Banking Platforms consisting of online and mobile banking allows customers to perform transactions, check balances, and manage accounts remotely. Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) and Point of Sales (POS) Terminals are physical devices that facilitates cash deposits, withdrawals and retail transactions. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Systems assists banks keep track of and manage their interaction with customers, helping banks personalize services and detect fraudulent activities. Payment processing systems facilitates digital transaction, including credit/debit card payments, interbank settlement and wire transfers. Security infrastructure this comprises of firewalls, intrusion detection/prevention systems (IDPS), multi-factor authentication (MFA), and data encryption mechanisms. Cloud banking services financial institutions have migrated to cloud-based environments, introducing new cybersecurity risks and vulnerabilities and lastly third-party service providers in which we know that banks rely on fintech companies, payment gateways and outsourced IT services, expanding their threat landscape.

Fig. 3. Basic Components of Banking Infrastructure.

Cybersecurity threats and attacks methods in banking

Banks are some of the most vulnerable institutions when it relates to cyber threats and cybercriminals exploit various vulnerabilities in banking systems using various sophisticated techniques. Below are a detailed and key reasons we need to take a look at these major threats faced by banks:

A. Payment and Transaction Systems

A payment and transaction system are the backbone of banking operations, enabling seamless financial transaction between businesses, individuals, and institutions. These systems make sure a secure, fast, and efficient processing of payments while maintaining compliance with financial regulations. Banks process billions of transactions daily through various networks. These networks include SWIFT which is the acronym for Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication and its job is to facilitate international bank to bank money transfers. ACH which also stands for Automated Clearing House and it used to process batch transaction for direct deposit, bill payments, and payroll and RTGS which stands for Real Time Gross Settlement and its sole duty is to handle large value of instant transactions between banks. These systems are designed for fast and secure money transfers but can be manipulated if the security is weak.

SWIFT attacks can occur when hackers gain access to bank terminals and send fraudulent transactions requests then they move on to the Man-in-the-Middle attacks where they intercept the transaction and modify the details before they reach the destination and then lastly, they move on to credential theft where hackers use phishing or malware to obtain login credentials of employees handling these transactions. For example, the Bangladesh Bank heist where the hackers infiltrated Bangladesh Bank’s system and sent transfer request via the SWIFT network, attempting to steal \$1 billion. While most transfer were blocked, \$81 million united states dollars was successfully transferred and remains largely uncovered.

The attackers exploited weak security measures, including outdated software and lack of firewalls, to access the SWIFT system [11]

B. Online and Mobile Banking Platform

As it is always noted that banks offer online and mobile banking services for customers to simply check balances, transfer money, and pay bills. These platforms are often also a main target for attacks. Customers usually access their accounts using their username, passwords and sometimes MFA and always transaction are authenticated using OTPs, biometric verifications, or security tokens. Attackers exploit these processes by using Phishing and Social Engineering using various patterns to trick users into revealing credentials through fake emails, calls or websites. They also use a form of Session Hijacking where attackers also steal session cookies to gain unauthorizes access and they also have SIM swapping where they trick providers into transferring a victim’s phone number to an attacker’s SIM for intercepting OTPs.

Fig. 4. Cyber threats in banking industry

For example, in 2016, Union Bank of India nearly lost \$171 million after employees fell victim to a phishing email, compromising the bank's credentials on the SWIFT network. The fraudulent transfer was detected and reversed in time [12]. This incident highlighted the effectiveness of phishing attacks and the critical need for employee awareness and training.

C. ATM and Point-of-Sale Systems

Banks operates ATMs and also process card transactions though point of sale terminals at merchant locations. ATMs communicate with banking servers to authentic withdrawals while POS terminals verify transactions using card chip/PIN or contactless payments. Attackers exploit these systems though skimming and shimmiing using hidden device installed on ATMs or POS machines to steal card data. They also use malware injection also known as jackpotting in which they install malware on ATMs to force cash withdrawals. Card cloning is another where they use stolen card details to create duplicate cards to withdraw cash.

D. Employee and Insider Threats

Employees at various banks have access to sensitive financial systems and can be targeted by attackers or become rogue insiders. Bank employees handle customer data, process transactions, and can access banking infrastructure. These attackers use attacks like spear phishing by sending highly targeted emails to employees to steal credentials, they sometimes use malicious insiders who are employees to leak data or plant malware for financial gain. For example, in 2024 JPMorgan Chase faced a cyberattack compromising data of around Seventy-Six (76) million households and about Seven (7) million small businesses. Attackers gained access using stolen employee login credentials, exploiting the lack of two-factor authentication on some servers [13]. The attackers navigate the network for months, gathering sensitive data. The breach highlights vulnerabilities in internal security protocols and the critical need for multi-factor authentication.

E. Ransomware and DDoS Attacks

Banks are often targets of cyber extortion, where hackers demand ransom to restore services. Ransomware encrypts banking data and demands payments while DDoS attacks flood bank servers to disrupt online banking services. Ransomware-as-a-Service (RaaS) is where Cybercriminals sell ransomware tools to attackers, DDoS-for-Hire Services is where attackers use botnets to overwhelm banking infrastructure and Exfiltration is when attackers threaten to leak customer data if ransom isn't paid. For example, in the case of Travelex Ransomware Attack (2020) the company was forced to pay \$2.3 million dollars in bitcoin to regain access to its system after attackers took control [14].

Fig. 5. Financial Impact of cyber security threats in banking industry

Malware injection involves embedding malicious software into bank's systems to facilitate unauthorized transaction, steal data, or disrupt operations. For example, in August 2018, Cosmos Bank in India suffered a significant cyberattack where hackers injected malware into the bank's ATM switch server. This allowed them to approve fraudulent transactions and clone debit cards. Over two days, approximately ₹94 crore (around \$13 million) was siphoned off through thousands of unauthorized ATM withdrawals across 28 countries [15]. The attackers bypassed the bank's core banking system, targeting the ATM switch directly. This sophisticated approach exploited vulnerabilities in the bank's infrastructure, highlighting the need for robust network segmentation and continuous monitoring.

VI. CYBER RISK ANALYSIS METHOD

The financial stability board FSB is a global organization that keeps an eye on the world's financial system and offers recommendations to help keep it stable and secure. Usually, it plays a key role in ensuring financial stability, including cybersecurity for banks and financial institutions. To protect banks from cyber-attacks, a set of protocols and procedures has been put in place, outlining both preventive and corrective action. These includes key aspect of cyber security management, as illustrated in Figure 6. FSB has created a detailed framework to help manage cyber risks in the financial sector, focusing on several key element [16] including, identification and protection, detection and monitoring incident response and recovery, information sharing and collaboration.

These elements are aimed at booster the financial sector's ability to withstand cyber threats, helping to ensure the stability and trustworthiness of financial systems around the world. Similarly, the Bank for International Settlements (BIS), through its Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS), sets cybersecurity guidelines for banks. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) also offers recommendations to support financial stability, while the World Economic Forum (WEF) Centre for Cybersecurity focuses on global strategies for financial cybersecurity. In addition to these efforts, various individuals and organizations have outlined specific guidelines and policies for managing cyber risks in internet banking [17].

Various models have been created to evaluate these risks, using a mix of qualitative insights and qualitative analysis. Combining qualitative and quantitative methods can provide a more comprehensive assessment of cyber risks. For instance, a study in the journal of operational risks introduces an adaptive model tailored for the financial and banking sector, integrating both qualitative assessments and quantitative metrics to evaluate information asset vulnerabilities [18]. A qualitative risk analysis is performed for risk assessment framework identifying potential cyber threats in [19]. In addition, evaluating vulnerabilities and assessing the impact on banking operations are also used to analyze different vulnerabilities. They often rely on expert judgement and structured processes to prioritize risks and develop mitigation strategies. Research has highlighted prevalent cyber threats such as phishing, malware ransomware, and insider threats. More critical risks in these banking institutions includes outdated systems, inadequate employee training, and insufficient security protocols. Addressing these weaknesses is crucial for enhancing overall cybersecurity resilience. A combination of interviews and surveys has been used to collect relevant information by [20] of an Australian banks cyber vulnerability, with emphasis on deposit balances, capital ratios and operation lose which proved to be a critical risk for the Australian bank in the finance industry.

The authors perform cyber risk analysis with the risk assessment framework based on FSB and BIS guidelines, following an expert judgement and structured process approach to prioritize risks and develop mitigation. Cyber security testing involves creating detailed scenarios of potential cyber incidents to understand their possible impacts and to develop response strategies. The study shows that banks prioritize managing cyber risk mainly to preserve customer trust, rather than simply to meet regulatory capital requirements. In the case of the Australian bank examined, this focus is evident in their adoption of a business-case approach to evaluating cyber threats. Through their control framework, they assess risks based on both inherent and residual exposure. However, the findings also highlight that if these risks aren't properly managed, the bank's operations and potentially its entire functionality could suffer significant damage.

Fig. 6. Elements of cyber risk management

A survey is conducted in [21] among members of the Global Cyber Resilience Group to explore cyber risks and the challenges they pose to central banks. The results highlight four key insights. First, there are clear differences between central banks in Advanced Economies (AEs) and those in Emerging Market Economies (EMEs) when it comes to how they perceive the frequency and cost of various cyber-attacks. Across the board, phishing and other forms of social engineering are seen as the most likely attack methods. However, AE central banks express greater concern over supply chain attacks compared to their EME counterparts. When it comes to the financial impact of cyber incidents, advanced persistent threats and ransomware are ranked as the most costly. When looking at who is behind these attacks, central banks in Advanced Economies (AEs) largely point to organized crime groups and state-sponsored actors as the main culprits. In contrast, Emerging Market Economy (EME) central banks identify organized crime along with individuals or activist groups as the primary threats. The survey also reveals that central banks are actively discussing and shaping policies to respond to cyber threats, with a noticeable increase in cybersecurity investments since 2020. Strengthening security controls and building cyber resilience have become top priorities in these investment efforts. Training current staff in cybersecurity and hiring new employees with the right expertise are seen as key priorities particularly among central banks in Emerging Market Economies (EMEs). But beyond staffing and investment, central banks are also focused on crafting clear and practical policy responses. A common priority among all central banks is the development of a formal strategy to address large-scale cyber-attacks on the broader financial system. To stay prepared, every central bank conducts internal simulations of cyber-attacks, with the most common scenarios involving attacks on their own systems or outages in payment systems and other critical financial market infrastructures (FMIs). Interestingly, while supervisory authorities in most EMEs have established frameworks for collecting data on cyber incidents affecting financial institutions, fewer than half of their counterparts in Advanced Economies (AEs) have done the same. Similarly, while nearly all central banks in Emerging Market Economies (EMEs) require supervised firms to report losses from cyber-attacks, only about two-thirds of central banks in Advanced Economies (AEs) have such a reporting requirement. Notably, no country currently mandates that these losses be disclosed publicly.

Third, central banks generally believe that the financial impact of a major, system-wide cyber-attack could be significant. Many also report that cyber-related losses in the financial sector have grown over the past year. Despite this, only a small number of central banks feel that the financial sector is fully prepared for such threats, and more than half of the respondents believe that cybersecurity investments have fallen short over the past year. Looking beyond traditional financial institutions, respondents indicated that fintech firms are seen as more vulnerable to cyber-attacks than big tech companies. However, most agree that if a big tech firm were successfully targeted, the overall financial impact would be much greater than that of an attack on a fintech.

Lastly, central banks in both Advanced Economies (AEs) and Emerging Market Economies (EMEs) already engage in extensive collaboration on a variety of issues. Bilateral partnerships, along with regional and global cooperation, are common practice. In AEs in particular, joint efforts tend to focus on key areas such as cyber resilience simulations, information sharing, and the development of policies to strengthen defenses against cyber threats. Among Emerging Market Economies (EMEs), central banks often work together on information sharing and developing cybersecurity policies. Additionally, more than two-thirds of them collaborate on creating common standards and protocols for the financial sector. The Bank for International Settlements (BIS) plays a key role in supporting these efforts, helping central banks strengthen cybersecurity and encouraging global cooperation—through initiatives such as its Cyber Resilience Coordination Centre and various projects under the BIS Innovation Hub.

Similarly, the impact of user behavior on the cybersecurity of banking systems is also examined in [22], where cyber attackers target the users of computer systems rather than the systems themselves. They use techniques like social engineering tricking individuals into revealing sensitive information like passwords or cognitive hacking, which involves spreading misinformation to manipulate user behaviour and gain access to networks or systems. According to [23], social engineering accounts for 28% of all cybersecurity attacks, with phishing alone responsible for 24% of those cases. According to reports from CyberEdge, over 70% of social engineering attacks have succeeded in recent years. Telstra's 2018 and 2019 reports also highlight human error as the leading vulnerability in cybersecurity. They reveal that phishing and its more targeted variant, spear-phishing were the most common types of attacks. These methods often combined social engineering tactics with fraud, tricking victims into installing malware or visiting fake websites to steal their login credentials.

The quantitative cyber risk assessment framework is one of the key tools used in the banking sector [24] presents a quantitative approach to assess cyber risk in the financial sector, analyzing various types of cyber incidents and identifying patterns to inform risk mitigation strategies. The framework provides information as to why financial institutions are highly exposed to cyber risks, vulnerabilities in financial sectors with major emphasis on single point of failure and critical infrastructure, business disruption in the financial sector, fraud and data breaches.

V. THREAT MITIGATION METHODS

Generally, the banking sector struggles with cybersecurity due to legacy systems, insufficiently secure firewalls, and the absence of comprehensive protective frameworks. Poor network security controls and very insufficient oversight exacerbate vulnerabilities, which can lead to non-compliance with industry standards. Additionally, weak governance over third-party risks exposes banks to potential breaches through service providers and vendors [25]. Thanks to strict regulatory oversight, significant investments in cybersecurity, and the adoption of advanced technologies, the banking sector faces far fewer cyberattacks compared to other industries. Secondly, investing in modern cyber security infrastructure while updating and patching systems regularly and enforcing robust data protection policies can help the banking sector mitigate threats and not put the entire bank in the hand adversaries. Banks need to prioritize technologies such as blockchain for secure transactions, machine learning algorithms for anomaly detection, and zero-trust architectures that enforce strict verification protocols. These investments will help create a multi-layered defense system capable of addressing complex threat landscapes [26].

A variety of frameworks and techniques have been introduced to reduce the likelihood of cyber risks. These include adopting the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF), implementing Zero-Trust Architecture (ZTA), and leveraging technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to detect and prevent cyber-attacks. For example, a NIST cyber security framework adopted by JP Morgan Chase, is presented in [27] that was used to strengthen its cyber security defense. The analysis recognized that cyber risk is a major threat to the financial system, necessitating substantial investment in cyber security. The company addressed both vulnerabilities and threats by using advanced tools such as artificial intelligence and cloud security. They built a multi-layered defence system with real-time monitoring and partnered with government and industry organizations to share threat intelligence and strengthen the protection of critical infrastructure. The AI-driven anomaly is basically used to quickly identify and isolate threats that are being utilized by attackers.

With increased threats to backend infrastructures a network segmentation is presented by [28] for IoT devices within the banks internal networks using DOS attack on a bank network.

Table II A Concise Summary of The Models Commonly Applied in Cyber Risk Analysis

Model	Application	Objective
NIST Framework	Guidelines for improving critical infrastructure cybersecurity	Provide structure approach to managing and reducing cyber security risks
Qualitative	Journal of operation risks analysis	Analyzing risks to evaluate information asset vulnerabilities.
Survey	Cyber Risk: Key Challenges Faced by Central Banks	Highlighting insights from central banks that are from Advance economies (AEs) and Emerging market economies (EMEs)
Interviewing	Human factors in cyber security	Emphasizing on the human factor leading to cyber-attacks
FSB and BIS	Cyber risk analysis with the risk assessment	To prioritize risks and develop mitigation.

The proposed approach involves exploiting a TCP-based protocol by overwhelming the victim's device with excessive data requests. This gradually consumes all available resources on the IoT device. The findings highlight three key layers of defence against Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks: detecting the attack, mitigating its impact, and preventing it from occurring in the first place. Along the same lines, a blockchain attribute-based secure data management model (BAB-SDMM) scheme is used in [29] that utilizes blockchain alongside attribute-based encryption in IoT banking systems. In the scheme, data aggregation is conducted securely, with each devices attribute and trust levels dynamically accessed. Results prove that once the devices attribute and trust levels are accessed, they will be granted an access, thus mitigating potential security threats.

This study [30] presents a framework designed to secure data provenance in Internet of Things (IoT) systems by integrating blockchain technology with access control policies. The framework is implemented using hybrid attribute-based encryption. Its effectiveness is evaluated by analyzing the computational cost and data throughput during encryption and decryption, as well as the strength of the encryption keys, measured using the avalanche effect. Experimental results show that the proposed system achieves lower computational costs and higher throughput. The setup and secret sharing times were evaluated based on the depth of the access control policy tree, while key generation time was analyzed in relation to the number of users. The decryption time was evaluated based on the number of attributes involved in the process. Additionally, the size of the ciphertext file was analyzed in relation to the length of the original plaintext. According to the avalanche effect, the encryption key demonstrated strong performance, with a calculated strength exceeding 99%.

Various threat modelling approaches have been developed and adopted to help banks analyze and mitigate cyber risks. One widely used model is STRIDE, created by Microsoft, which classifies security threats into six main categories: spoofing, tampering, repudiation, information disclosure, denial of service, and privilege escalation. This framework helps systematically identify and address potential security threats and vulnerabilities in banking systems, enabling authorities to respond effectively and resolve these issues in a timely manner. DREAD is another risk mitigation model that assesses threats by evaluating five key factors: how easily the threat can be reproduced, the potential damage it can cause, the number of users it could affect, how easily it can be exploited, and how likely it is to be discovered [31]. Damage potential refers to how severe the impact would be on both the user and the system if the threat were to occur. Reproducibility is the ease with which the threat can be replicated meaning creating an easy access for the threat to be repeated. TRIKE is an open-source modeling methodology that can integrate risk management and defense perspectives. Trike mainly focuses on defining acceptable risk levels for assets and analyzing potential threats to ensure these levels are maintained [32]. Attack Trees approach uses trees structures to represent potential attack paths, helping organizations visualize and analyze how system vulnerabilities might be exploited. It's particularly useful in understanding complex attacks scenarios in banking infrastructures. ThreatModeling-LMM is a novel framework that automates threat modeling for bank systems in the form of using large language models (LLMs). It operates through datasets creation, prompt engineering and model fine-tuning to enhance threat identification and mitigation [33].

VI. INDUSTRY

The Banking Industry are experiencing significant advantages through the adoption of IoT Technologies which are now improving operational efficiency and security measures. Within Banking facilities, IoT-powered systems help to detect threats and irregularities by proving real time monitoring and data collection through the security Cameras and sensors. This allows Banks to quickly identify all suspicious activities and prevent unauthorized access [34].

Fig. 7. IoT Technologies In Banking Industry

A). IoT Technologies In Banking Industry

1. Biometric authentication

Biometric authentication, a key IoT-driven security feature, enhances banking Operations by implementing technologies such as facial recognition and fingerprint scanning. These methods ensure technology that only authorized customers and employees can access specific areas or perform transactions. To support these security measures, banks must maintain a secure database that stores biometric data, requiring advanced encryption and algorithms [35]. This not only prevent unauthorized access but enhances customer experience by making transactions faster and more secure [36].

2. Blockchain Technology for secure Transactions

Blockchain technology plays a vital role in improving the accuracy and reliability of financial transactions. It creates a secure, tamper-proof record of every transaction, reducing the risk of fraud and ensuring that financial data remains transparent and trustworthy. By integrating IoT width block chain, Banks can achieve a higher level of security in their financial operations.

3. Intelligent Monitoring and customer experience.

IoT-based smart monitoring systems allows banks to analyze customer behavior by using interconnected sensors. These sensors can track customer movement, waiting times, and service preferences.

For example, if a bank notices that customers spend too much time waiting, it can adjust staffing levels or optimize service points to improve the efficiency. This data-driven approach helps enhance customer satisfaction while streamlining operations.

4. Automation and operational Efficiency

Another major advantage of IoT in Banking is Automation [37]. Now banks use IoT devices to automate essential operations, such as ATM maintenance alerts, security monitoring, and cash flow management. These smart systems can instantly detect malfunctions and send real-time alerts, reducing downtime and minimizing the need for human intervention. As result, Banks can operate more smoothly and efficiently.

B). IoT Security Goals in Banking Industry

Because IoT devices handle a vast amount of sensitive financial data, they are a prime target for cyberattacks. To ensure security, banks follow these key IoT security principles:

Fig. 8. IoT Security Goals

1. Authorization

Only authorised users and devices should have access to banking systems and resources to prevent breaches.

2. Data Integrity

Ensuring that transaction data remains accurate, untampered and secure through processing.

3. Confidentiality

Sensitive banking information must be protected from unauthorised access using encryption and secure protocols.

4. Authentication

Only verified users or systems should be allowed to interact with IoT banking networks.

5. Availability

IoT-based banking services must remain accessible to authorized users without interruptions or failures

6. No repudiation:

All transactions and interactions should be trackable and verifiable, ensuring that no one can deny their involvement in a financial operation

C). How will managed services propel the IoT in Banking Industry?

The increasing importance on managed services is enhancing IoT in banking by proposing specialised support and infrastructure management. Financial organisations that hold complex IoT solutions require expert assistance to efficiently deploy, integrate and maintain these systems [38]. Managed services provide a comprehensive strategy, including system setup, ongoing monitoring and technical assistance. This outsourcing strategy enables banks to focus on their core financial operations while assuring that their IoT systems are handled by professionals capable of optimizing performance and resolving issues quickly.

Additionally, the demand for operational efficiency and cost management coals the expansion of managed services in the IoT sector. Financial institutions face issue of administering and sustaining advances IoT technology in-house, which may be time consuming and expensive. Managed services that adapt to the needs of the organisation.

This methodology eliminates the need for substantial capital investments and minimizes operational costs, allowing financial institutions to adopt and deploy IoT solutions without incurring considerable expenses

D. Future trends and opportunity

In nowadays IoT is transforming banking services by enabling smart automation, real time transactions and enabled security. As artificial Intelligence, 5G, and Blockchain continue to advance, the Banking Industry will further leverage IoT for smart financial advisory, and seamless customer experiences [39].

The future of banking will increasingly involve interactions not just between people and banks but between networks of intelligent devices managing financial transactions autonomously in the background of daily life. However Banks must address challenges such as cybersecurity risks and regulatory compliance to ensure the safe and efficiency of implementation of IoT-driven banking solutions [40]. The IoT will redefine financial services, making banking intelligent, automated and customer-centric.

VII. DISCUSSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In nowadays IoT is transforming banking services by enabling smart automation, real time transactions and enabled security. The IoT-enabled banking solutions such as smart ATMs, wearable banking devices, sensor-equipped branches, and connected payment systems have opened up new ways for banks to interact with customers and monitor physical assets.

A). Personalized Customer Service

One of the key advantages of using IoT in banking is its ability to deliver personalized customer service, tailored to individual needs and preferences. With IoT devices collecting real-time behavioral data, banks can tailor products and services to meet specific needs, offering a more engaging experience. Additionally smart branches equipped with sensors and connected devices can optimize energy use, reduce operational costs, and monitor foot traffic to improve branch layout and staffing.

B). Risk management and security

Risk management and security are other critical areas enhanced by IoT. By leveraging connected surveillance systems and biometric sensors, banks can better secure physical infrastructure. Also, real time monitoring of ATM status and other hardware prevents downtime and tampering.

Despite these advancements, the challenges remain substantial. The most pressing concerns are cybersecurity Threats, data privacy regulations, scalability and integration, and cost of infrastructure.

Cybersecurity: Banks must invest heavily in security IoT ecosystems against breaches and unauthorized access because the number of connected devices grows [41], so does the attack surface

Cost of infrastructure: Maintaining and deploying IoT infrastructure at scale demands high capital expenditure and ongoing operational costs.

Data Privacy and Regulations: compliance with data protection laws such as GDPR, CCPA, and others becomes complex when handling data from diverse sources [42].

Scalability and Integration: Integrating legacy banking systems with modern IoT devices requires significant investment and technical expertise.

C). Future trends

The integration of the IoT devices in the Banking industry is expected to redefine service delivery, customer engagement and operational Efficiency. Future trends indicate a move toward personalized banking experiences using real-time data collected from IoT-enabled devices such as smartphones. These technologies enable banks to deliver tailored financial services and location-based customer support. IoT is enhancing security and automation through biometric-enabled ATMs, contactless payments and intelligent branches that respond dynamically to customer behavior. The use of Block chain in combination with IoT is also being explored to secure transactions through decentralized, tamper-proof records. However, this rapid adoption presents cybersecurity challenges including device-level vulnerabilities, data interception and system manipulation. To mitigate such risks, banks are investing in zero trust architectures, end-to-end encryption, secure firmware updates, and AI-based intrusion detection systems.

IoT will also play a crucial role in predictive maintenance of banking infrastructure, real time credit scoring using behavioral data, and optimizing smart breaches with sensors-driven automation.

As artificial Intelligence, 5G,Blockchain continue to advance, the Banking Industry will further leverage IoT for smart financial advisory, and seamless customer experiences [43]. The future of banking will increasing involve interactions not just between people and banks but between networks of intelligent devices managing financials transactions autonomously in the background of daily life. However Banks must address challenges such as cybersecurity risks and regulatory compliance to ensure the safe and efficiency of implementation of IoT-driven banking solutions [40]. The IoT will redefine financial services, making banking intelligent, automated and customer-centric.

As IoT continue to progress, its role in banking will become more general, demanding not only technological advancement but also adaptive security frameworks. The future of Banking lies in secure [44], smart and context-aware systems driven by the synergy between IoT Innovation and cybersecurity resilience.

CONCLUSION

As technology continues to evolve rapidly, the adoption of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies has helped the banking sector advance significantly particularly in areas such as smart ATMs, enhanced communication, and improved security. While digital transformation brings numerous benefits to the banking industry, it has also significantly increased the sector's vulnerability creating new opportunities and methods for cyber-attacks. This study explores the key cybersecurity threats facing the banking industry, such as data breaches, unauthorized access, malware attacks, and the exploitation of IoT devices. It is observed that the importance of robust encryption, multi-factor authentication, real-time monitoring, and AI-driven threat detection needs to be taking into serious consideration to safeguard financial assets and customer data. Many banking staff members lack the necessary training or expertise to effectively respond to cyber-attacks, and as a result, cybersecurity is often not given the attention it deserves within banking operations. Although various systems have been implemented, many of them rely on outdated, partially functional, or impractical software that falls short in real-world applications. Additionally, the existing security devices and frameworks are often complex and lack clearly defined standard operating procedures.

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